

The Effect of Good Corporate Governance Principles on Patient Satisfaction in the Hospital Bahagia City of Makassar

Andi Muhammad Dzulkifli¹, Muhammad Alwy Arifin², A. Ummu Salmah³, Darmawansyah⁴, Amran Razak⁵, Nurhaedar Jafar⁶

¹Postgraduate School Program Hasanuddin University, Indonesia

^{2,3,4,5,6}Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Andi Muhammad Dzulkifli

ABSTRACT

The concept of Good Corporate Governance is applied not only in the field of private companies but also in the public sector, including very broad fields such as in the fields of education, police, transportation and health as well as social services. This study aims to analyze the relationship of the principles of Good Corporate Governance to the satisfaction of inpatients in the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City. This study uses a type of quantitative research using a cross-sectional design. Proportional sampling is calculated using the Slovin formula obtained by 83 samples. To analyze the effect of Good Corporate Governance variables on patient satisfaction, data were analyzed using the Chi-Square test. The results showed that there was a relationship between the principle of transparency ($p = 0,000$), accountability ($p = 0,000$) and responsibility ($p = 0,000$) on patient satisfaction. It is recommended that the hospital maintain and further improve the quality of service, among others by giving more time in listening to complaints and patient expectations, the ease of getting patients information about health services and the availability of inpatient rooms and maintaining the cleanliness of the inpatient room.

Keywords: Good Corporate Governance, Patient Satisfaction, Hospitalization.

INTRODUCTION

Good Corporate Governance is a concept to improve fairness, transparency, accountability, and responsibility which is currently recommended for business institutions (Trisnantoro, 2005). There are

several things that can be done by the leadership to implement the GCG principles, among others, to provide equal opportunities for all employees to participate in all activities, meetings and training for all employees based on the ability and expertise of the employees concerned and to hold meetings with employees to determine the steps strategic at least once a year. (Nurwahida et al., 2012)

In developed countries the concept of governance is applied not only in the field of private companies but also in the public sector, including very broad fields such as in the fields of education, police, transportation and health as well as social services. Moreover, the community also demands the same thing about good governance in public services. (Sitohang, 2014).

To improve the application of the principles of Good Corporate Governance to hospitals, health care providers should pay attention to 4 factors including transparency, accountability, responsibility and fairness (Moeljono, 2005).

The hospital operated in December 2012, the Hospital helps people who need health services. And is a prime and comprehensive health service center that emphasizes capabilities that are fast, precise, accurate, trustworthy and professional at affordable costs and by always prioritizing customer satisfaction in the Bahagia Hospital. (Profil Rumah Sakit Bahagia Kota Makassar, 2019).

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between the principles of Good Corporate Governance based on the principles of transparency, accountability and responsibility for the satisfaction of inpatients at the Bahagia Hospital, Makassar City.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and design of the study

This research was conducted in Bahagia Hospital, Makassar City in 2019. This study used a type of quantitative research using a cross-sectional study design.

Population and Samples

Determination of the total population of this study based on the average number of visits of patients each month as many as 463 patients. Proportional sampling is calculated using the Slovin formula obtained by 83 samples. Respondents were aware and able to communicate well and were willing to be interviewed.

Method of collecting data

After all data has been collected using a questionnaire filled out by respondents, the stages of data editing are done by checking the possibility of errors in filling out or filling in data that is not filled by respondents, coding the data by giving the answer code number filled in by respondents to facilitate data processing, data tabulation done after giving the code for each answer given by the respondent with the help of a computer, cleaning data is done so that every data that has been obtained is error free before the statistical analysis is done with the SPSS computer program, and the presentation in table form is accompanied by an explanation.

Data analysis

Data to find out the relationship between variables in the test variable is a comparative analysis using the Chi-square statistical test.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that respondents, who stated good transparency and good satisfaction, were 71 respondents (93.4%) while those lacking were 5 respondents (6.6%). Respondents who stated lack of transparency and satisfaction of good respondents were 3 respondents (42.9%) while those who stated they were less satisfied were 4 respondents (57.1%). There is an effect of transparency on the satisfaction of inpatients in the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City ($p = 0,000$).

Table 2 shows that respondents, who stated good accountability and good satisfaction were 73 respondents (93.6%) while those who were less satisfied were 1 respondent (20%). Respondents who stated lack of accountability and good satisfaction were 5 respondents (6.4%) while those who stated were less satisfied as much as 4 respondents (80%). There is an influence of accountability on the satisfaction of inpatients in Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City ($p = 0,000$).

Table 3 shows that respondents, who stated good responsibility and good satisfaction were 70 respondents (93.3%) while those who were less satisfied were 5 respondents (6.7%). Respondents who stated lack of responsibility and good satisfaction were 4 respondents (50%) while those who stated were less satisfied as much as 4 respondents (50%). There is an effect of responsibility on the satisfaction of inpatients in the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City ($p = 0,000$).

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of the Principles of Transparency of Bahagia Hospitals in Makassar City

Transparency	Satisfaction				Total (N)	Percentage (%)	P. value
	Good		Not Good				
	n	%	n	%			
Good	71	93,4	5	6,6	76	100	0,000
Not Good	3	42,9	4	57,1	7	100	

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of the Principles of Accountability of Bahagia Hospitals in Makassar City

Accountability	Satisfaction				Total (N)	Percentage (%)	P. value
	Good		Not Good				
	N	%	n	%			
Good	73	93,6	5	6,4	78	100	0,000
Not Good	1	20,0	4	80,0	5	100	

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of the Principles of Responsibility of Bahagia Hospitals in Makassar City

Responsibility	Satisfaction				Total (N)	Percentage (%)	P. value
	Good		Good				
	n	%	n	%			
Good	70	93,3	5	6,7	75	100	0,000
Not Good	4	50,0	4	50,0	8	100	

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research and data processing that has been carried out, this discussion will explain in accordance with the objectives of the study, namely "to analyze the principles of Good Corporate Governance in this case is the principle of transparency, accountability and responsibility for the satisfaction of inpatients at Bahagia Hospital Makassar city.

According to the National Committee on Governance in the General Guidelines for Good Public Governance in Indonesia in 2008, transparency contains elements of disclosure and provision of adequate information and is easily accessible to stakeholders. Transparency is needed so that supervision by the community and the business community on the implementation of activities can be carried out objectively.

The results of the analysis using the Chi Square test indicate that there is a relationship between the principle of transparency and patient satisfaction at the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City with a value of $p = 0,000$. Respondents' answers to the principle statement of transparency are also dominated by good categories, especially in respondent's statement of appearance to hospital staff and clerical explanations, all respondents stated well, but in the statement of the ease of obtaining inpatient rooms and information on the price of service respondents expected to be improved.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Lamadjido et al. (2013) with quantitative research design and cross sectional approach in analyzing the application of the principles of Good Corporate Governance to patient satisfaction at Anutapura Palu Hospital in 2013, obtaining results there is a relationship between principles transparency with patient satisfaction. And the same results in Marniati's (2010) research on employees in the General Administration Section of the Regional General Hospital Dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh.

According to the National Committee on Governance Policy in the General Guidelines for Good Public Governance in Indonesia in 2008, accountability contains elements of clarity of functions within the organization and how to account for them. Accountability is needed so that each state institution and state administrator performs their duties responsibly.

Respondents' answers to the statement of accountability principles were also dominated by good categories, especially in the statement of the assessment of the timing of drug administration, feeding and waiting times for doctor examinations and laboratory staff skills needs to be improved.

The results of the analysis using the Chi Square test indicate that there is a relationship between the principle of accountability and patient satisfaction with a value of $p = 0,000$. This is in line with the results of a study conducted by Surbakti

(2010) at Tanjung Morawa North Sumatra's PTPN II (Persero) employee who showed that there was a relationship between the principle of accountability and employee satisfaction, even though the measurement variable was different because it was intended for employee satisfaction.

Responsibility is an active involvement, if in an organization, of course, from every organizational actor and other stakeholders in supporting the increase in organizational value. From this definition we can understand that the top management (Head of Bureau), referred to as the holder of organizational control. Thus in addition to the three parties we can categorize it as not the main participant but as a supporting participant. What participants do is certainly called participation. Participation in question is the fulfillment of responsibilities, rights, and authority as well as other actions that should be taken by someone according to his position (Sedarmayanti, 2004).

Respondents' answers to the responsibility principle statement were also dominated by good categories, especially in the statement of the hospital's assessment of the management of medical and non-medical waste. All respondents stated good, but in the statement the cleanliness of the inpatient room and bathroom of the respondents hoped to be improved.

The results of the analysis using the Chi Square test indicate that there is a relationship between the principle of responsibility and the satisfaction of respondents in the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City with a value of $p = 0,000$. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Lamadjido et al (2013) in his research analyzing the application of the principles of Good Corporate Governance to patient satisfaction at Anutapura Palu Hospital in 2013.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of this study, it was found that there was a relationship

between the principles of transparency, accountability and responsibility for the satisfaction of inpatients in the Bahagia Hospital of Makassar City. It is recommended that the hospital maintain and further improve the quality of services, among others, giving more time in listening to complaints and patient expectations, the ease of getting patients information about health services and the availability of inpatient rooms and maintaining the cleanliness of inpatient rooms (floors, blankets, bed linen) and bathrooms.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Idrus, M., Mallongi, A., and Ibrahim, J. 2016 Surveillance System Model for Pulmonary Tuberculosis Suspected in Pangkep Region, Indonesia. *Curr. Res. Tuberculosis*, 1, 1-7
- Komite Nasional Kebijakan Governance. (2008). *Pedoman Umum Good Public Governance Indonesia*. Jakarta : Komite Nasional Kebijakan Governance
- Lamadjido R.A., Darmawansyah. & Noor N.B. (2013). *Penerapan Prinsip Good Corporate Governance Terhadap Kepuasan Pasien di RSUD Anutapura Palu*. *Jurnal AKK*, 2(2):1-9
- Marniati. (2010). *Analisis Penerapan Prinsip Good Corporate Governance (GCG) Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Bagian Administrasi Umum Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah DR. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh (Tesis)*. Medan : Universitas Sumatera Utara
- Moeljono, D. (2005). *Good Corporate Culture Sebagai Intidari Good Corporate Governance* Jakarta: Elex Computindo.
- Nurwahida, A.W., Hamzah, A. & Arifin, A. (2012). *Hubungan Prinsip-prinsip Good Corporate Governance Dengan Kinerja Pegawai di Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Wajo Tahun 2012*. Makassar: Universitas Hasanuddin.
- Rumah Sakit Bahagia Kota Makassar. (2019). *Profil Rumah Sakit Bahagia, Makassar*.
- SS Russeng, Lalu Muhammad Saleh, Devintha Virani, Ade Wira Listrianti Latief, Anwar Mallongi., 2018. The Investigation of the Lactic Acid Change among employee of national electrical Power. *Indian Journal*

- of Public Health Research & Development 9 (1) 2018
- Sedarmayanti. (2004). *Good Governance (Kepemerintahan yang Baik)*. Bandung : Mandar Maju
 - Surbakti, R. (2010). *Pengaruh Penerapan Prinsip – Prinsip Good Corporate Governance terhadap Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia (SDM) Studi Pada Kantor PTPN III (Persero) Tanjung Morawa (Skripsi)*. Medan : Universitas Sumatera Utara
 - Sitohang, E. (2014). Prinsip Hukum Dalam Tata Kelola Rumah Sakit. *Jurnal Yuridika*, 29(1):83-99
 - Trisnantoro, L. (2005). *Aspek Strategis Manajemen Rumah Sakit*. Yogyakarta: Andi.

How to cite this article: Dzulkifli AM, Arifin MA, Salmah AU. et al. The effect of good corporate governance principles on patient satisfaction in the hospital Bahagia city of Makassar. *International Journal of Science & Healthcare Research*. 2019; 4(3): 81-85.
